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A Tristable **Cross-shaped** Unsymmetric Fiber-reinforced Cross-ply Laminates: Experimental and Simulation Methods

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PART ONE INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTIONS

Dai, F., Li, H., and Du, S., 2013, "A multi-stable lattice structure and its snap-through behavior among multiple states," *Composite structures*, 97, pp. 56-63.

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PART TWO

EXPERIMENT AND SIMULATION

Fig. 1. Geometry of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates.

(1) configuration A (2) configuration C (3) configuration B
Fig. 2. Three stable configurations A, C and B of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminate

(1) Configuration A (2) Configuration C (3) Configuration B
Fig. 7. The cross-shaped laminate with three stable configurations A, C and B using the FEM.

EXPERIMENT

Fig. 3. The assembly of the three dimensional scanner.

Fig. 4. The assembly of universal tensile testing machine.

SIMULATION

Fig. 8. The assembly of each part.

Fig. 6. Finite element model and stacking arrangement of the unsymmetric cross-shaped laminate in ABAQUS.

EXPERIMENT AND SIMULATIONS

(a) snap-through process: A-C-B

S, Mises
SNEG, (fraction = -1.0), Layer = 1
(Avg: 75%)
+8.590e+07
+7.959e+07
+7.329e+07
+6.697e+07
+6.066e+07
+5.435e+07
+4.804e+07
+4.173e+07
+3.543e+07
+2.912e+07
+2.281e+07
+1.650e+07
+1.019e+07

(b) Configuration C

S, Mises
SNEG, (fraction = -1.0), Layer = 1
(Avg: 75%)
+5.115e+07
+4.762e+07
+4.408e+07
+4.054e+07
+3.701e+07
+3.347e+07
+2.993e+07
+2.640e+07
+2.288e+07
+1.932e+07
+1.578e+07
+1.224e+07
+7.711e+06

(a) Configuration A

(b) snap-back process: B-C-A

S, Mises
SNEG, (fraction = -1.0), Layer = 1
(Avg: 75%)
+7.791e+07
+7.397e+07
+7.003e+07
+6.609e+07
+6.215e+07
+5.821e+07
+5.427e+07
+5.033e+07
+4.638e+07
+4.244e+07
+3.850e+07
+3.456e+07
+3.062e+07

(c) Configuration B

Fig. 10. Three stable shapes of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates from the numerical simulation

Fig. 5 The snapping process, including (a) snap-through process: A-C-B and (b) snap-back process: B-C-A, between different stable equilibrium configurations.

PART THREE

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Comparison between the experimental and numerical results

(a) Configuration A

(b) Configuration C

(c) Configuration B

Fig. 13. The geometric shapes of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates from the experiment and numerical simulation

Fig. 11. Comparison of load-displacement curves of snap-through process Fig. 12. Comparison of load-displacement curves of snap-back process

- Reinforced material
- The thickness of single layer
- Sidelength

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

➤ Reinforced material

The principal curvature

Specimens	R_{1e}	R_{2e}	R_{3xe}	R_{3ye}	R_{1f}	R_{2f}	R_{3xf}	R_{3yf}
T700	A	7.9968	8.2968	8.1065	/	8.3826	8.5438	8.4680
	C	8.2418	8.1947	1.6079	1.1811	8.7387	8.6052	1.7044
	B	8.1537	7.9867	/	8.0176	8.5742	8.4031	/
T300	A	11.329 6	11.423 8	11.481 2	/	12.114 0	12.232 4	12.2896
	C	11.494 7	11.505 3	2.6349	0.3328	12.334 2	12.410 3	2.5864
	B	11.537 6	11.514 5	/	11.479 2	12.386 3	12.240 8	/

Snap
Load

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

➤ The thickness of single layer

Snap Load

The principal curvature

Specimens	R_{1e}	R_{2e}	R_{3ye}	R_{3yf}	R_{1f}	R_{2f}	R_{3yf}	R_{3yf}
0.10mm	A	14.2326	14.2271	14.5764	/	15.0243	15.0772	15.3993
	C	14.1936	14.2763	2.4206	1.3965	14.9058	15.0750	2.6198
	B	14.3144	14.3212	/	14.3953	15.2711	15.1474	/
0.15mm	A	7.9968	8.2968	8.1065	/	8.3826	8.5438	8.4680
	C	8.2418	8.1947	1.6079	1.1811	8.7387	8.6052	1.7044
	B	8.1537	7.9867	/	8.0176	8.5742	8.4031	/
0.20mm	A	7.4217	7.4603	7.4522	/	7.3839	7.5038	7.5552
	C	7.9856	7.6964	1.4739	0.8846	7.9217	7.7484	1.4929
	B	7.8206	7.5109	/	7.5044	7.6097	7.4889	/

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Sidelength

Snap Load

Specimens		R_{1e}	R_{2e}	R_{3xe}	R_{3ye}	R_{1f}	R_{2f}	R_{3yf}	R_{3yf}
50mm	A	7.9968	8.2968	8.1065	/	8.3826	8.5438	8.4680	/
	C	8.2418	8.1947	1.6079	1.1811	8.7387	8.6052	1.7044	1.0905
	B	8.1537	7.9867	/	8.0176	8.5742	8.4031	/	8.4812
40mm	A	7.7362	8.0394	8.0102	/	7.9306	8.4354	8.1968	/
	C	8.1166	7.9250	2.2390	1.5937	8.3124	8.1325	2.4007	1.6694
	B	7.9051	7.8693	/	8.1902	8.1138	7.8324	/	8.2005
30mm	A	7.5402	7.2930	8.1629	/	7.7187	7.3299	8.3596	/
	C	/	/	/	/	8.0465	8.3530	4.4276	2.0602
	B	7.4925	7.2601	/	8.1403	7.4738	7.2785	/	8.3334

The principal curvature

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